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ЭКСПЕРИМЕНТАЛ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ ЭКСПЕРИМЕНТАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ | JOURNAL OF EXPERIMENTAL STUDIES

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OBSTETRIC HEMORRHAGE: MODERN MANAGEMENT TACTICS

ANNOTATION

Obstetric bleeding remains a significant cause of maternal death worldwide. In the structure of OB, which led to an unfavorable outcome of pregnancy and childbirth, an important place belongs to postpartum hemorrhage. OB is the cause of a critical condition, as a rule, with massive blood loss and the development of disorders in the hemostasis system in a situation of incorrect tactics for providing obstetric care. If a pregnant woman approaches childbirth against the background of hypo coagulation or severe thrombophilia with impaired hemostasis, massive bleeding should be expected. But, based on modern experience, it can be prevented and intensive therapy can be carried out correctly.

Keywords: maternal mortality, obstetric bleeding, prothrombin complex coagulopathy.

АКУШЕРСКИЕ КРОВОТЕЧЕНИЯ: СОВРЕМЕННАЯ ТАКТИКА ВЕДЕНИЯ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Акушерские кровотечения остаются значимой причиной материнской смертности во всем мире. В структуре акушерских осложнений, приведших к неблагоприятному исходу беременности и родов, важное место принадлежит послеродовым кровотечениям. Акушерство является причиной критического состояния, как правило, при массивной кровопотере и развитии нарушений в системе гемостаза в ситуации неправильной тактики оказания акушерской помощи. Если беременная женщина приближается к родам на фоне гипокоагуляции или тяжелой тромбофилии с нарушением гемостаза, следует ожидать массивного кровотечения. Но, основываясь на современном опыте, это можно предотвратить и правильно провести интенсивную терапию.

Ключевые слова: материнская смертность, акушерские кровотечения, протромбиновая комплексная коагулопатия.

АКУШЕРЛИК ҚОН КЕТИШИ: ЗАМОНАВИЙ БОШҚАРУВ ТАКТИКАСИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Акушерлик қон кетиши дунё бўйлаб оналар ўлимининг муҳим сабаби бўлиб қолмоқда. Ҳомиладорлик ва туғилишнинг ноқулай натижасига олиб келган акушерлик асоратлари таркибида туғруқдан кейинги қон кетиш муҳим ўрин тутди. Акушерлик оғир ҳолатнинг сабаби, қоида тариқасида, катта қон йўқотиш ва нотўғри акушерлик ёрдами тактикаси ҳолатида гемостаз тизимидаги бузилишларнинг ривожланиши. Агар ҳомиладор аёл гипокоагуляция ёки гемостаз бузилган оғир тромбофилия фонида туғилишга яқинлашса, катта қон кетишини кутиш керак. Аммо замонавий тажрибага асосланиб, бунинг олдини олиш ва интенсив терапияни тўғри бажариш мумкин.

Калит сўзлар: оналар ўлими, акушерлик қон кетиши, протромбин комплекси коагулопатияси.

Introduction

Obstetric hemorrhage is an absolutely emergency situation that requires the simultaneous participation of many specialists. It is advisable to create special teams consisting of the head (the administrator of the medical institution, his deputy for obstetrics or the responsible obstetrician-gynecologist), the direct organizers of care: the heads of the obstetric department and the anesthesiology-reanimation department, as well as employees of the obstetric department and the anesthesiology-reanimation department.

Maternal mortality (MM) is a key indicator of the health status of women of reproductive age and an indicator of the performance of a country's healthcare system, reflecting both the availability and quality of prenatal and obstetric care. The high rate of MM from obstetric bleeding (OB) reflects the poor quality of the organization of medical care and indicates the availability of reserves to reduce maternal losses. OB remain a significant cause of maternal death worldwide. In the structure of OB, which led to an unfavorable outcome of pregnancy and childbirth, an important place belongs to postpartum hemorrhage. OB are the cause of a critical condition, as a rule, with massive blood loss and the development of disorders in the hemostasis system in a situation of incorrect tactics for providing obstetric care [1, 3, 7, 11].

According to the WHO, approximately 14,000,000 births occur annually in the world, which are complicated by postpartum hemorrhage, of which 120,000-140,000 are accompanied by severe complications and death (50% in the first 24 hours), and 200,000 lead to female disability.

In the United States, massive blood loss during childbirth is considered to be 12% of maternal deaths, of which 73% of the case can be provided with qualified care, while in the UK it is considered that the mortality rate from this category of blood loss ranks third, and in 53% of cases can be provided with timely assistance. In Africa, the maternal mortality rate from major bleeding is 35-60%. according to the National Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, maternal mortality from obstetric bleeding is 25.8% [4, 10, 14, 18].

Considering that multiple causes of massive bleeding and hemorrhagic shock can be prevented in obstetrics, it is important to adhere to the emergency medical care protocol for patients in this category, since all diagnostic and therapeutic measures are limited [5, 13, 17].

Changes in the activity of organs and systems occur, primarily due to the systems of blood coagulation and platelet hemostasis, an increase in the concentration and activity of natural coagulants leads to the development of coagulation syndrome [6, 8, 15, 16].

Due to massive blood loss, pathological phenomena develop in the body, the most important of which are a decrease in the volume of circulating blood with the subsequent development of hypotension, hypoxemia and hypoxia, organ hypo perfusion and metabolic acidosis, as well as activation of all links of the coagulation system with the possible development of disseminated intravascular micro thrombosis.

A consequence of massive blood loss is also dilutional coagulopathy, that is, coagulopathy due to dilution and loss of coagulation factors. Further progression of disorders of the hemostasis system leads to the rapid development of multiple organ failure and uncontrolled coagulopathy bleeding. The progression of multiple organ failure and the development of uncontrolled coagulopathy bleeding can only be prevented by intensive replenishment of clotting factors [9, 12].

For a long time, the drugs of choice for the correction of coagulopathy of various origins were blood components - FFP and cryoprecipitate. In recent years, plasma and recombinant coagulation factors have been an alternative to blood components, used both along with FFP and cryoprecipitate, and instead of them. One of these drugs is a prothrombin complex concentrate (PCC), which contains coagulation factors II, VII, IX, X and proteins C and S. PCC has 100% bioavailability, its administration causes an increase in the level of vitamin K-dependent coagulation factors in plasma blood and can rapidly correct coagulation disorders in patients deficient in one or more of these factors [2].

The concentrate of the human prothrombin complex Octaplex contains several coagulations factors II-220-760 IU, factors VII-80-480 IU, as well as a complex of anticoagulants: protein S-140-640 IU, protein C-140-620 IU, heparin 100-250 IU. The presence of both pro- and anticoagulants makes the drug quite safe in terms of thrombogenicity.

Thus, in the prenatal period, an important role is played by the assessment of the severity of adaptive changes in the hemostasis system and the prediction of hemorrhagic complications in the period of preparation for childbirth. Many studies have shown that underdevelopment of the hemostasis system during pregnancy has been found to lead to bleeding during childbirth in 15% of cases. Decompensation of hemostatic potential leads to massive bleeding.

The purpose of the study

Improvement of complex treatment of obstetric bleeding based on the development of a method for early detection of the risk of its development.

Materials and research methods

This study was conducted at the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center for Obstetrics and Gynecology from January to May 2021. The prothrombin complex concentrate was used to eliminate obstetric bleeding. Letters of consent were obtained from a patient participating in the study and Octaplex-500 was used.

The dose of Octaplex was 1 ml/kg or 25 IU/kg. The rate of administration is 1-3 ml/min. 1 vial was administered for approximately 6-7 minutes. The use of 2-3 vials of the drug in almost all cases prevented bleeding, in 89% of cases it was possible to save the organ, and during this time, compared to 2020, maternal mortality due to obstetric bleeding decreased by 5.5 times.

We divided the women who participated in our study into 2 groups according to the parameters of coagulation hemostasis and hemogram. Group 1 included 120 patients who received octaplex for massive obstetric bleeding, group 2 included 60 patients who received traditional intensive therapy specified in national protocols. Pregnant women of groups I and II of comparison did not differ significantly in age and parity. The predominant age ranged from 18 to 35 years, which corresponds to the most active reproductive age. There were 42 women (35%) who were primiparas in the main group, 37 (30%) multiparous and 41 women (35%) who had multiple births.

Women of the main group and the comparison group had previously had childhood infections (measles, chickenpox, mumps). Surgical interventions such as tonsillectomy, appendectomy was carried out by 34 women (28.4%) of the 1st group and 15 women (18.8%) of the 2nd groups.

The onset of menarche practically did not differ in the compared groups. The duration of the menstrual cycle in both groups is 28-30 days thus, the examination of the patients of the studied groups showed the identity of age, the duration of the menstrual cycle and the onset of menarche.

Clinical blood analysis was performed in venous blood on an automatic hematological analyzer Sysmex-KX-21N. Blood for research was taken from the cubital vein into a plastic or silicone tube containing 3.8% sodium citrate solution - 9:1. The blood was centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 15 min. Centrifugation was carried out immediately after blood sampling, and plasma was taken for research immediately after centrifugation. The following indicators were assessed: the number of erythrocytes, leukocytes, hemoglobin and platelet levels, hemotacrit, and blood clotting time.

Evaluation of hemostasis system parameters was carried out on an automatic analyzer Sysmex –CA 50 blood coagulation: fibrinogen, D-dimer, partially activated thromboplastin time (APTT), prothrombin index (PTI), thrombin time (TI), international normalized ratio (INR).

Research results.

Studies on the analysis of the effectiveness of treatment in patients participating in the study showed that only 2 of the 9 studied parameters (20%) changed significantly - hemoglobin increased from 90.8±0.6 g/l to 94.5±0.9 (P<0.05), and the number of leukocytes decreased from 9±0.9×10⁹ to 8.2±0.8 (P<0.05). All other indicators remained at the level of indicators before treatment (P>0.05). This applies to segmented and stab neutrophils (P> 0.05), the relative number of neutrophils (P> 0.05), the relative number of monocytes (P> 0.05), hematocrit (P> 0.05) and ESR (P> 0.05).

Table 1. Peripheral blood parameters of patients participating in the study

Indicators	Reference indicators	1-group	2-group
Erythrocytes, 10 ¹² /l	4,2±0,2	3,9±0,2	2,9±0,3
Hemoglobin, g/l	123,8±0,5	128,5±0,4	94,5±0,9
Leukocytes, 10 ⁹ /l	5,8±0,5	5,3±0,9	8,2±0,8
Neutrophil/I, %	3,1±0,6	5,6±1,0	7,8±1,2
Neutrophils, s / i, %	57,4±1,0	58,7±1,5	50,6±1,1
Lymphocytes, %	19,3±1,1	25,8±1,4	22,6±1,3
Monocytes, %	3,1±0,2	6,3±0,5	4,9±0,7
Hematocrit, %	36,7±0,1	32,5±0,8	28,8±1,2
ESR, mm/h	10,2±0,3	13,9±0,6	19,7±0,9

• Note: * - differences are significant for group 1 (*- P<0.05, * * - P<0.01, * * * - P<0.001), ^ - differences are significant for group 2 (^- P< 0.001).

The results obtained showed that the traditional treatment was ineffective in the examined patients. Thus, there was no significant effect on the peripheral blood parameters of patients who were engaged in the traditional method of treatment. The effectiveness of treatment in patients included in this group was 22.0%. In patients of the 1st group, that is, when using the drug we offer, a significant difference was found from the studied indicator 9 (89.0), with the exception of the relative parameter of monocytes, the data were not mutually significant - respectively 5.5 ± 0.8% before treatment and 6.3±0.5% after treatment (P>0.05).

It should be noted that the number of erythrocytes significantly increased 1.41 times 2.8±0, from 1x10¹²/L to 3.9±0.2x10¹²/L, P<0.05, hemoglobin increased 1.28 times (from 100,4±0.5 g/l to 128.5±0.4 g/l, P <0.05), the number of leukocytes decreased by 1.78 times (from 9.6±1, T/or neutrophils decreased by 1.92 times (from 10.8±1.0% to 7.8±1.0%, P <0.001), there was an increase in s/or neutrophils by 1.27 times (from 45.9±1.7% up to 58.7±1.5%, P <0.05). The hematocrit index after treatment increased by 1.20 times from 27.3±0.8% to 32.5±0.8% (P <0.005), ESR decreased by 1.35 times, respectively - from 19.7±0, 9% to 13.9±0.6% (P <0.05).

The results obtained indicate the high efficiency of the new treatment method, which is recommended for use in relation to peripheral blood parameters. Thus, the study of peripheral blood parameters before and after bleeding in women from the recommended treatment showed that 9 out of 9 studied parameters (90.0%) significantly changed in a positive direction (P <0.05).

Of the 7 listed parameters, all (100%) have changed significantly and in different directions. If the APTT, PT, INR decreased significantly compared to the control data ($R < 0.05$ - $R < 0.001$), it was found that from the data presented it can be seen that the thrombin time increased compared to the control fibrinogen, D-dimer, PTI ($P < 0.05$ - $P < 0.001$).

Table 2. Indications for coagulation hemostasis in study patients

Indicators	Reference indicators	1-group	2-group
APTT, sec	27,3±0,5	38,1±1,0	34,2±1,0
PV, sec	12,1±0,1	16,4±0,1	12,1±0,2
Thrombin time hour, sec	13,3±0,5	16,2±0,8	15,0±0,9
Fibrinogen, g/l	2,4±0,4	4,7±0,7	5,8±1,3
D-dimer, ng/ml	231,6±24,6	604,9±35,2	1103,8±57,9
INR	0,9±0,05	0,9±0,06	0,6±0,08
PTI, %	81,4±0,4	83,6±0,3	86,3±0,4

Note: * - differences are significant for group 1 (*- $P < 0.05$, ** - $P < 0.01$, *** - $P < 0.001$), ^ - differences are significant for group 2 (^ - $P < 0.001$).

It should be noted that traditional treatment does not have a sufficiently pronounced effect on the parameters of coagulation hemostasis.

A comparative study of indicators of coagulation hemostasis in patients of the 2nd group before and after traditional treatment showed that the effectiveness of treatment was only 26.8%.

As can be seen from Table 2, before the start of the recommended treatment in patients of the 1st group, almost all hemostasis parameters were significantly changed. Indicators of coagulation hemostasis increased compared to control values ($P < 0.05$ - $P < 0.001$). From the studied indicators of coagulation hemostasis, it can be seen that 6 indicators increased accordingly, this change is 86.7%.

It should be noted that almost all parameters have reached the level of normal values. APTT increased to 38.1 ± 1.0 sec, 1.35 times the value before treatment ($P < 0.05$). A similar trend was observed in PTT, where the increase was 1.55 times ($P < 0.05$). A significant decrease in the amount of fibrinogen can be seen from the table. It can be seen that the amount of D-dimer significantly decreased compared to the 2nd group ($P < 0.001$).

Thus, if the effectiveness of treatment in providing assistance to the traditional method is 28.5%, then from the above indicators we can also find out that 85.6% of the result can be achieved when helping patients using the method we proposed.

Conclusions

Therapeutic effect. Treatment of massive bleeding in patients with bleeding complications using Octaplex allows these diagnosed patients to improve the quality and effectiveness of treatment, reduce the duration of treatment; the use of prothrombin complex preparations in massive obstetric bleeding ensures a rapid restoration of the action of procoagulants in the treatment and prevention of coagulopathy, maintaining the mutual proportionality of their systems against blood clotting and blood clotting, and at the same time it is indicated that they are important for practice in reducing the incidence of maternal mortality, increasing efficiency treatment and prevention of coagulopathy;

The introduction of Octaplex in the treatment of women with complications from massive bleeding makes it possible to carry out early prevention of the disease, as well as to improve the method of treatment.

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